

MATERNAL USE OF LOCAL HERBALS IN MATERNITY CARE IN NAKASEKE, UGANDA: PREVALENCE, CIRCUMSTANCES, AND OUTCOMES

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cross-sectional design. The target population consisted of 3,571 women of reproductive age, from which a sample of 268 participants was selected using Cochran's formula

Introduction

The use of traditional herbs in maternity care has remained widespread and longstanding across many societies, particularly in rural regions. In Uganda and other African countries, women frequently rely on herbal medicine during pregnancy, childbirth, and postpartum recovery. This practice has persisted over generations despite improvements in biomedical care. Women turn to herbs for various reasons, including affordability, cultural beliefs, trust in traditional knowledge, and positive past experiences (Tassew et al., 2024). Herbs are commonly used to relieve pregnancy-related discomforts, speed up labour, prevent miscarriage, or support postpartum healing. In many cases, the influence of older family

members or traditional birth attendants strongly sustains these practices (Tuasha et al., 2023).

The World Health Organization (WHO) defines traditional medicine broadly, encompassing not only herbs but also knowledge, skills, and practices grounded in indigenous cultural beliefs and experiences. This may include plants, animal parts, minerals, massage techniques, and spiritual therapies. Such practices are often used in diagnosis, treatment, or prevention of illness, as well as for general well-being. Importantly, they continue to coexist with modern healthcare systems, particularly in contexts where biomedical services are limited, inaccessible, or mistrusted (WHO, 2001; Nyeko et al., 2016).

In simpler terms, local herbs refer to plant-based extracts prepared in different forms without formal pharmaceutical processing, but known to prevent, heal, or alter disease progression. Many are used for accelerating labour or relieving discomforts (Adane et al., 2020). These herbs

can take the form of roots, leaves, flowers, extracts, or finished herbal products, provided they contain active ingredients. They are usually self-administered, often on the advice of family members or community healers, with limited consultation of trained health professionals (Tuha et al., 2020).

Globally, approximately 55% of pregnant women use herbal medicines during maternity care (Illamola et al., 2020). Popular examples include green tea, ginger, fenugreek, garlic, and peppermint (Adane et al., 2020). Other long-used herbal supplements such as blue cohosh and black cohosh serve as uterine stimulants and labour inducers (Illamola et al., 2020). Some communities use vegetables like bangun bangun and katuk leaves to promote breastmilk production (Silalahi et al., 2020). The choice of herbs, however, varies across ethnic groups and geographical regions depending on cultural traditions and climate.

In Africa, reliance on herbs is particularly high, with about 80% of women using traditional remedies during pregnancy, labour, or the postpartum period (Adane et al., 2020). Across Sub-Saharan Africa, between 40% and 90% of pregnant women are estimated to use herbal remedies (Fukunaga et al., 2020). In Tanzania, for instance, 60–70% of the population depends on local herbs for healthcare (Fukunaga et al., 2020). In rural Uganda, including Nakaseke, disparities between formal health services and everyday realities make herbal use particularly common. Women often skip antenatal care visits or find that the advice offered is not aligned with

their lived experiences. Herbs are perceived to bridge this gap, although their safety and long-term effects are not fully understood.

In Uganda's central region, about 40% of pregnant women use herbal medicines alongside modern pharmaceuticals (Tumuhais et al., 2021). This co-use contributes to continued high maternal and neonatal mortality (Laelago et al., 2016). In Nakaseke District, the burden of herbal medicine use remains undocumented, yet observations from maternity services suggest widespread use. Factors driving reliance include affordability, availability, perceptions of efficacy, and the friendlier nature of herbalists compared to health workers, who are often considered rude or unapproachable. Other determinants include maternal age, rural residence, cultural norms, education, marital status, and antenatal attendance (Fukunaga et al., 2020).

Herbs are used for diverse reasons: managing nausea, headaches, backache, or striae gravidarum; inducing or augmenting labour; relieving gastrointestinal issues; providing energy; bathing mother and infant for good fortune; or treating skin and respiratory conditions (Adane et al., 2020). Nabirye and Najjemba (2021) observed universal herbal use in pregnancy, with the highest usage during the first trimester. Nambatya et al. (2020) also observed that 63.5% of pregnant women at Uganda's referral hospital reported using herbs, mainly for backache, nausea, and miscarriage prevention. Aloe vera and chamomile were frequently cited.

Nevertheless, risks associated with herbal use are considerable, especially among women with comorbidities such as epilepsy or asthma (Illamola et al., 2020). At Mulago Hospital, 6% of abortion-related admissions involved prior herbal use (Tumuhais et al., 2021). Animal studies indicate possible fetal loss, abnormal organ development, and skeletal changes following exposure to certain herbs like ginger or *Rhizoma coptidis* (Belayneh et al., 2022). Other adverse outcomes include uterine rupture, preterm delivery, congenital abnormalities, neonatal heart failure, and postpartum haemorrhage (Fukunaga et al., 2020). Tuha et al. (2020) also documented maternal complications, with 3.3% of herbal users reporting stillbirths and 13% experiencing miscarriages.

Modern maternity interventions such as iron supplementation, malaria prophylaxis, and oxytocin for labour augmentation are widely available (Sambili et al., 2016). Yet preference for herbs persists, raising concern about interactions, overdoses, and the absence of regulatory guidelines. The risks are further magnified by cultural reliance and the secrecy that often surrounds herbal use.

Several studies have examined determinants of herbal use, including religion, tribe, employment status, and antenatal attendance (Tumuhais et al., 2021). Yet, in Nakaseke District, where use is especially high documentation of prevalence and outcomes remains sparse. This gap is problematic given the potential health risks and the continued dependence on herbs in the

community. A deeper understanding of the patterns, motivations, and consequences of herbal medicine use is therefore necessary.

Investigating these practices is not intended to dismiss cultural knowledge but rather to provide evidence that can guide interventions. Policymakers, healthcare providers, and community leaders need reliable information to design appropriate maternal health strategies. These may involve discouraging unsafe herbal practices, integrating safe remedies into formal care with regulation, or strengthening health education that aligns with women's experiences. In this way, research into herbal use during maternity care offers both cultural respect and opportunities for improved maternal and neonatal health outcomes.

Statement of the Problem

The prevalence, circumstances, and outcomes of herbal medicine use in maternity care among women in Nakaseke District, Uganda, highlight a critical dimension of the country's maternal and neonatal health challenges. Global targets under Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) 3 aim to reduce maternal mortality to fewer than 70 per 100,000 live births and neonatal mortality to fewer than 12 per 1,000 live births by 2030 (WHO, 2025a). Uganda, however, remains far from achieving these benchmarks, with a maternal mortality ratio of 189 per 100,000 live births and a neonatal mortality rate of 22 per 1,000 live births (WHO, 2025b). While biomedical strategies such as antenatal visits, skilled birth attendance, oxytocin use, neonatal resuscitation, and effective referrals have been

promoted, widespread reliance on traditional herbal medicines continues to shape maternity practices, particularly in rural districts such as Nakaseke.

These traditional practices are driven by cultural beliefs, accessibility, and perceptions of effectiveness, yet they often lack scientific validation, dosage regulation, or professional oversight. Women commonly consume herbal remedies alongside modern interventions, exposing themselves to risks such as uterine overstimulation, obstructed labour, haemorrhage, and drug interactions. At the same time, some mothers perceive herbals as beneficial for managing pregnancy discomforts, inducing labour, or supporting postpartum recovery. This duality creates a gap in understanding: the actual extent of use, the specific circumstances under which women turn to herbals, and the maternal and neonatal outcomes that result. Investigating these dimensions in Nakaseke District is therefore essential to generate evidence that can inform culturally sensitive yet medically sound interventions. Such evidence will not only help to reduce preventable maternal and neonatal deaths but will also guide Uganda's efforts to

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study.

1. What is the prevalence of herbal medicine use in maternity care among the women in Nakaseke, Uganda?

2. What are the circumstances under which the mothers take the local herbals in maternity care?

3. What are the outcomes of local herbals' application in the maternity care among the mothers in Nakaseke town council?

Methodology

Study Design and Setting

The study adopted a descriptive cross-sectional design, which measures outcomes and exposures simultaneously in participants (Setia, 2016). This approach was chosen because it is both time-efficient and cost-effective. The research was conducted in Nakaseke Town Council, located in central Uganda, approximately 66 kilometres northwest of Kampala. Nakaseke lies at an elevation of about 4,186 feet above sea level, giving it a relatively cooler climate compared to surrounding low-lying areas.

Population and Sample

The study population comprised women of reproductive age who had ever given birth in Nakaseke Town Council, estimated at 3,571. From this population, a sample of 268 women was selected using Cochran's formula and random sampling. Quantitative data were obtained through researcher-administered questionnaires translated into the Luganda dialect to ensure comprehension. For illiterate participants, a trained research assistant read the questions aloud and recorded responses. The questionnaires were mainly closed-ended to maintain consistency and facilitate analysis. Validity was ensured through expert review for clarity, relevance, and completeness, while

Data Collection, Analysis, and Ethics

reliability was established through a pretest in Nyimbwa Sub-County, Luwero District, involving 11 women. Feedback led to revisions that improved wording and consistency.

Results and Discussion

Table 1: socio-demographic data of the respondents

Variable	Comment	Frequency(N)	Percentage (%)
Age(Years)	15-24	49	18.3
	25-34	68	25.4
	35-45	91	34.0
	Above 45	60	22.4
Educational qualification	Uneducated	62	23.1
	Primary	73	27.2
	Secondary	74	27.6
	Tertiary institution	59	22.0
Marital Status	Single	86	32.1
	Married	109	40.7
	Divorced	35	13.1
	Widowed	38	14.2
Number of children	<4	94	35.1
	4-6	71	26.5
	>6	103	38.4
Religion	Catholic	65	24.3
	Anglican	77	28.7
	Born Again	62	23.1
	Islam	64	23.9

Source: Primary Data 2025 (Respondents)

Most respondents were in the age group 35–45 years (91; 34.0%), followed by 25–34 years (68; 25.4%), over 45 years (60; 22.4%), and 15–24 years (49; 18.3%). Educational attainment showed that 74 (27.6%) had low–mid-level education, 73 (27.2%) had incomplete primary,

62 (23.1%) had no education, and only 59 (22.0%) attained tertiary education. Marital status revealed that 109 (40.7%) were married, 86 (32.1%) never married, 38 (14.2%) widowed, and 35 (13.1%) divorced. Household size was generally large, with 103 (38.4%) reporting six or more children, 71 (26.5%) having four to six, and

94 (35.1%) having four or fewer. Religious affiliation was almost evenly spread: Anglicans

77 (28.7%), Catholics 65 (24.3%), Muslims 64 (23.9%), and born-again Christians 62 (23.1%).

Source: Primary Data 2025 (Respondents)

Figure 1: Prevalence of the use of herbal medicines in maternity care

The findings in Figure 2 show that a vast majority of respondents, 245 (91%), reported using traditional herbal medicine, while only 23 (9%) did not. This high prevalence underscores the

community’s heavy reliance on herbal remedies, reflecting trust, cultural acceptability, affordability, and generational familiarity. Herbal medicine is often used as a first or second line of treatment, complementing modern healthcare.

Table 2: Sources and Timing of Herbal Medicine Use among Respondents

Variable	Comment	Frequency(N)	Percentage (%)
Source of the herbal medicines	Myself	27	10.1
	My mother	109	40.7
	My aunt	48	17.9
	Traditional birth attendant	55	20.5
	Others (Grandmother)	6	2.2
	N/A	23	8.6
Time of use of the herbal medicines	During pregnancy	130	48.5
	During labor	69	25.7
	After delivery	46	17.1
	N/A	23	8.6

Source: Primary Data 2025 (Respondents)

The data in Table 2 show that most respondents, 109 (40.7%), obtained herbal medicines from their mothers, highlighting the central role of maternal figures in women’s health decisions. Traditional birth attendants were the second most common source (55; 20.5%), followed by aunts (48; 17.9%), while a smaller number (27; 10.1%) collected herbs themselves, reflecting personal initiative. Grandmothers were

mentioned rarely (6; 2.2%), and 23 (8.6%) gave no response. In terms of timing, nearly half (130; 48.5%) used herbal medicine during pregnancy, 69 (25.7%) during labour, and 46 (17.1%) after delivery, with 23 (8.6%) not specifying. These findings underline the strong influence of family networks and traditional caregivers, as well as the consistent use of herbal medicines throughout the maternity cycle.

Table 2: Frequency and percentage distribution of responses on local herbs used and their routes of administration

Variable	Response	Frequency	Percent age
Local herb used			
Emumbwa	Yes (Orally)	84	31.3
	Yes (Vaginally)	10	3.7
	Yes (Topically)	21	7.8
Ebombo	Yes (Orally)	39	14.6
	Yes (Vaginally)	9	3.4
	Yes (Topically)	60	22.4
Olweza	Yes (Orally)	12	4.5
	Yes (Vaginally)	1	.4
	Yes (Topically)	97	36.2
Namirembe	Yes (Orally)	6	2.2
	Yes (Vaginally)	6	2.2
	Yes (Topically)	76	28.4
Route of administration			
Emumbwa	No	142	53.0
	Yes	11	4.1
Ebombo	No	149	55.6
	Yes	11	4.1
Olweza	No	143	53.4
	Yes	15	5.6
Namirembe	No	172	64.2

	Yes	8	3.0
Others	Yes	23	8.6
	No	245	91.4

The findings in Table 3 show that a few key herbs dominate local practice, each with its own preferred form of use. Emumbwa stood out as the most recognised, with nearly a third of respondents (31.3%) taking it orally, usually as a drink, while smaller numbers used it on the skin or vaginally. Ebombo, on the other hand, was more often applied to the skin (22.4%), though some also took it orally (14.6%), reflecting its use for both external and internal conditions. Olweza was particularly associated with topical use,

mentioned by over a third (36.2%) of respondents, while oral or vaginal applications were rare. Namirembe was the least used, largely applied to the skin (28.4%), with very limited use otherwise and a majority of respondents reporting no experience with it at all. A small group (8.6%) mentioned other herbs, but most did not, suggesting that practices in the community tend to concentrate on a few familiar remedies rather than a wide range of traditional plants.

Figure 2: Percentage distribution of reason for using the local herb

Source: Primary Data 2025 (Respondents)

The results in figure 2 show that most respondents turned to herbal medicines because they were seen as cheap and easy to use, with 155 (57.8%) highlighting affordability and

accessibility as the main reasons. In many households, particularly in rural or semi-urban settings, such remedies are valued because they are familiar, home-prepared, and do not require costly medical consultations. Social influence

also played a role, as 32 respondents (11.9%) reported using herbs due to peer or community pressure, reflecting the strength of cultural norms and shared practices. Other reasons included a belief in greater effectiveness compared to modern treatments (26; 9.7%), the perception that herbs are free from overdose risks (20; 7.5%), and a preference for natural

products (13; 4.9%). A small number (22; 8.2%) gave no specific reason, suggesting either routine, unquestioned use or deeper cultural and spiritual motivations. Overall, the findings highlight how economic constraints, social networks, cultural beliefs, and perceptions of safety and naturalness all converge to sustain the widespread use of herbal medicines.

Table 3: Respondents’ frequency and percentage distribution of response on circumstance of using local herbs

Circumstance for use	Response	Frequency	Percentage
Nausea and vomiting or morning sickness	Yes	41	15.3
	No	227	84.7
Cough	Yes	144	53.7
	No	124	46.3
Common cold	Yes	17	6.3
	No	251	93.7
Headache	Yes	88	32.8
	No	180	67.2
High blood pressure	Yes	39	14.6
	No	229	85.4
Abdominal pain or indigestion	Yes	44	16.4
	No	224	83.6
Urinary tract infection	Yes	52	19.4
	No	216	80.6
Malaria	Yes	95	35.4
	No	173	64.6
Back pain	Yes	42	15.7
	No	226	84.3
Vaginal problems like itching, bleeding, infections and abnormal discharge	Yes	63	23.5
	No	205	76.5
Stomach ache	Yes	86	32.1
	No	182	67.9
Health of child	Yes	45	16.8

	No	223	83.2
Pregnancy symptoms like pains and general aches	Yes	26	9.7
	No	242	90.3
Labour stimulation	Yes	69	25.7
	No	199	74.3
Avoiding unwanted big size of the fetus	Yes	20	7.5
	No	248	92.5
Making labour fast and easy	Yes	41	15.3
	No	227	84.7
Improving lactation	Yes	29	10.8
	No	239	89.2
Improving the course of pregnancy	Yes	32	11.9
	No	236	88.1
Successful peer pressure	Yes	15	5.6
	No	253	94.4
Others	Yes	9	3.4
	No	259	96.6

Source: Primary Data 2025 (Respondents)

The results in Table 4 reveal that women relied on herbal medicines for a wide range of health conditions, covering both general illnesses and pregnancy-related needs. The most frequent reasons were cough (144; 53.7%) and malaria (95; 35.4%), reflecting the role of herbs as an accessible first line of treatment where formal health care may be limited. Common everyday complaints such as headaches (88; 32.8%) and stomach upsets (86; 32.1%) were also widely treated with herbs, showing their place in day-to-day household health management. Maternal and reproductive health formed another important area of use. Vaginal complaints such as itching, infection, or discharge were reported by 63 women (23.5%), while 69 women (25.7%)

used herbs to stimulate labour, reflecting strong cultural expectations around herbal support during childbirth. Other pregnancy-related conditions such as urinary tract infections (52; 19.4%), nausea and vomiting (41; 15.3%), back pain (42; 15.7%), and abdominal cramps (44; 16.4%) were also commonly managed with herbal remedies. Beyond maternal care, 45 respondents (16.8%) used herbs for infant and child health, highlighting intergenerational application. Less common but notable reasons included aiding lactation (29; 10.8%), supporting normal pregnancy progression (32; 11.9%), relieving pregnancy pains (26; 9.7%), preventing a baby from becoming too large (20; 7.5%), colds (17; 6.3%), and peer influence (15; 5.6%). A small group (9; 3.4%) cited other

social purposes throughout pregnancy, childbirth, and childcare.

personal or traditional reasons. Together, these findings show that herbs are woven into women’s health practices, serving medical, cultural, and

Table 4: Respondents’ frequency and percentage distribution of response on outcome of local herb use

Outcome	Response	Frequency	Percentage
Negative			
Stillbirth	Yes	78	29.1
	No	190	70.9
Baby appearing older than gestational age at birth	Yes	63	23.5
	No	205	76.5
Vaginal bleeding	Yes	87	32.5
	No	181	67.5
Uterine hyper stimulation and rupture	Yes	64	23.9
	No	204	76.1
Caesarean section	Yes	75	28.0
	No	193	72.0
Preeclampsia	Yes	67	25.0
	No	201	75.0
Nausea and vomiting	Yes	81	30.2
	No	187	69.8
Fetal distress	Yes	71	26.5
	No	197	73.5
Low neonatal birth weights	Yes	85	31.7
	No	183	68.3
Miscarriages	Yes	85	31.7
	No	183	68.3
Retention of the placenta	Yes	61	22.8
	No	207	77.2
Separation of the placenta	Yes	60	22.4
	No	208	77.6
Obstructed labour	Yes	72	26.9
	No	196	73.1

Neonatal jaundice	Yes	71	26.5
	No	197	73.5
Others	Yes	2	.7
	No	266	99.3
Positive			
Prevented evil spirits	Yes	69	25.7
	No	199	74.3
Prevented invasive procedures like forceps deliveries	Yes	90	33.6
	No	178	66.4
Prevented acid reflux (heartburn)	Yes	99	36.9
	No	169	63.1
Improved fertility	Yes	113	42.2
	No	155	57.8
Softened the abdomen enabling easy kicking by the baby and prevented striae gravidarum	Yes	114	42.5
	No	154	57.5
Reduced period of labor	Yes	113	42.2
	No	155	57.8
Others	Yes	6	2.2
	No	262	97.8

Source: Primary Data 2025 (Respondents)

The results in Table 5 paint a mixed picture, showing both dangerous complications and positive experiences linked to the use of herbal medicines during pregnancy and childbirth. On the negative side, many women reported serious outcomes: vaginal bleeding (87; 32.5%), nausea and vomiting (81; 30.2%), stillbirths (78; 29.1%), and caesarean sections (75; 28.0%). Other complications included low birth weight and miscarriages (85 each; 31.7%), fetal distress and neonatal jaundice (71 each; 26.5%), obstructed labour (72; 26.9%), and preeclampsia (67; 25.0%). Less frequent but still concerning were uterine hyperstimulation or rupture (64; 23.9%), retained placenta (61; 22.8%), and placental

separation (60; 22.4%). Despite these risks, respondents also highlighted several perceived benefits. Many associated herbal use with softening of the abdomen and prevention of stretch marks (114; 42.5%), enhanced fertility and shorter labour (113; 42.2%), and relief from heartburn (99; 36.9%). Others felt herbs helped them avoid invasive procedures such as forceps delivery (90; 33.6%) or offered protection against evil spirits (69; 25.7%), underscoring the cultural and spiritual weight of these practices. Only a handful (6; 2.2%) mentioned other benefits, suggesting that most positive outcomes were tied to a few widely shared beliefs.

Table 5: Model summary for circumstances of herbal medicine use by respondents

Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.425 ^a	.181	.114	.383

a. Predictors (Constant)

The regression analysis in Table 6 showed a moderate positive relationship (R = 0.425) between herbal medicine use and its circumstances. However, the model explained only 18.1% of the variation (Adjusted R² =

11.4%), indicating weak explanatory power. The standard error of 0.383 further suggests moderate deviation between predicted and actual outcomes, highlighting that many other factors influence herbal medicine use beyond those captured in the model.

Table 7: ANOVA^a on the coefficients for circumstances of using herbal medicine

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	8.001	20	.400	2.724	.000 ^b
	Residual	36.278	247	.147		
	Total	44.280	267			
a.	Dependent Variable: Prevalence of use of herbal medicines					
b.	Predictor (constant)					

Source: Primary Data 2025 (Respondents)

The ANOVA results in showed that the regression model was statistically significant (F = 2.724, p < .001), confirming that the predictors, taken together, had a meaningful influence on herbal medicine use. However, the model explained only a small portion of the

variance (R² = 0.181; Adjusted R² = 0.114), indicating that while the predictors were significant, their practical explanatory power was limited. Much of the variation is likely driven by other social, cultural, economic, or health factors not captured in the model.

Table 8: Herbal medicine use Vs Outcome of the herbal medicine use

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	-1.073	.484		-2.217	.028
	Nausea and vomiting or morning sickness	.002	.073	.002	.028	.978

Cough	.208	.052	.255	3.982	.000
Common cold	-.052	.104	-.031	-.502	.616
Headache	.066	.059	.076	1.113	.267
High blood pressure	.038	.081	.033	.467	.641
Abdominal pain or indigestion	-.096	.083	-.088	-1.166	.245
Urinary Tract infection	.049	.068	.048	.729	.467
Malaria	.113	.060	.133	1.898	.059
Back pain	.088	.068	.078	1.290	.198
Vaginal problems like itching, bleeding, infections and abnormal discharge	.093	.066	.097	1.394	.165
Stomach ache	.071	.057	.082	1.246	.214
Health of child	.071	.075	.066	.952	.342
Pregnancy symptoms like pains and general aches	.017	.084	.012	.203	.839
Labour stimulation	.096	.066	.103	1.439	.152
Avoiding unwanted big size of the fetus	.114	.103	.074	1.104	.271
Making labour fast and easy	.054	.078	.047	.687	.493
Improving lactation	.069	.084	.053	.826	.410
Improving the course of pregnancy	-.038	.082	-.030	-.459	.647
Successful peer pressure	.055	.111	.031	.489	.625
Others	.219	.139	.097	1.577	.116

a. Dependent Variable: Prevalence of use of herbal medicines

Source: Primary Data 2025 (Respondents)
The coefficients analysis showed that among the health conditions tested, only cough had a statistically significant influence on herbal

medicine use ($B = 0.208, p < .001$). This indicates that respondents who reported using herbs for cough were much more likely to use herbal remedies in general. Malaria ($p = .059$)

showed a borderline association, while other conditions such as headaches, stomach pain, nausea, and labour induction had p-values well above 0.05, suggesting little or no predictive

power. Overall, cough emerged as the strongest and most consistent driver of herbal medicine use, reflecting the deep-rooted cultural reliance on herbs for respiratory ailments.

Table 9: Coefficient analysis results for outcome of the herbal medicine use

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	-.393	.622		-.632	.528
	Stillbirth	-.007	.068	-.008	-.107	.915
	Baby appearing older than gestational age at birth	.047	.066	.049	.707	.480
	Vaginal bleeding	.049	.062	.056	.794	.428
	Uterine hyperstimulation and rupture	.003	.069	.003	.047	.963
	Caeserean section	.049	.063	.054	.778	.437
	Preeclampsia	.027	.066	.028	.401	.689
	Nausea and vomiting	.077	.059	.087	1.300	.195
	Fetal distress	-.005	.068	-.005	-.067	.947
	Low neonatal birth weights	.012	.066	.014	.185	.854
	Miscarriages	.024	.066	.028	.368	.713
	Retention of the placenta	.015	.070	.015	.212	.832
	Separation of the placenta	.011	.073	.011	.146	.884
	Obstructed labour	.000	.065	.000	-.005	.996
	Neonatal jaundice	.015	.068	.017	.227	.821
Others	-.142	.302	-.030	-.469	.640	
Prevented evil spirits	.122	.058	.131	2.095	.037	

Prevented invasive procedures like forcep deliveries	.072	.057	.084	1.265	.207
Prevented acid reflux (heartburn)	.116	.053	.137	2.204	.028
Improved fertility	.068	.057	.082	1.194	.234
Softened the abdomen enabling easy kicking by the baby and prevented striae gravidarum	.120	.057	.146	2.111	.036
Reduced period of labour	.022	.063	.027	.356	.722
Others	.192	.176	.070	1.088	.278

a. Dependent Variable: Prevalence of use of herbal medicines

The regression results in Table 9 showed that three positive outcomes significantly predicted herbal medicine use. Belief in protection against evil spirits ($B = 0.122$, $p = 0.037$), relief from heartburn ($B = 0.116$, $p = 0.028$), and softening of the abdomen with prevention of stretch marks ($B = 0.120$, $p = 0.036$) all increased the likelihood of use. These findings highlight how spiritual beliefs, physical comfort, and cosmetic considerations shape women’s decisions. By contrast, adverse outcomes such as stillbirth, miscarriages, or uterine complications had no significant effect, suggesting that fears of harm did not deter women from using herbs. Overall, the results indicate that positive expectations and cultural values carry more weight than risks in influencing maternal choices about herbal medicine.

Discussion of Findings

The Prevalence of the Local Herbs Use

The results showed that 91% (245/268) of the women reported using herbal preparations at some stage of their pregnancy, while only 9% (23/268) said they had not used them at all. This points to a very high prevalence of herbal medicine use in Nakaseke Town Council, even higher than levels reported in many other contexts. For instance, Tumuhaise et al. (2021) recorded 79% in Uganda, while studies in Ethiopia reported much lower levels, with Tuha et al. (2020) at 48.9% and Adane et al. (2020) at 47.77%. Belayneh et al. (2022) found 51.2% in northeastern Ethiopia, El Hajj et al. (2020) reported 57.8% in Zambia, and Fukunaga et al. (2020) noted just 10.9% in Tanzania’s Kigoma region. Outside Africa, Shewamene et al. (2020) reported a prevalence of 72.3% in Australia. The study also considered when women used these remedies. Almost half (130; 48.5%) reported using them during pregnancy, 69 (25.7%) during labour, and 46 (17.1%) after delivery, while a

smaller group (23; 8.6%) did not specify the timing. Together, these findings suggest that pregnancy is the period when herbal medicines are most commonly used, followed by labour and the postpartum stage. This highlights the importance of shaping maternal health policies that improve access to safe biomedical care while also acknowledging local practices, guiding women toward safer choices without disregarding cultural realities.

Circumstances under which the mothers take the local herbals during maternity care:

The regression findings showed that cough was the only condition significantly predicting herbal use ($B = 0.208$, $p < .001$), confirming it as a major driver of traditional treatment. This is consistent with El Hajj et al. (2020), who reported that 81.3 per cent of pregnant women in Lusaka Province, Zambia, relied on herbal remedies to manage cough, underlining its salience as a motivator for traditional care. Malaria and “other” conditions approached statistical significance but did not reach the conventional threshold. Nevertheless, studies such as Babalola et al. (2021) have shown that malaria is frequently managed with herbal remedies, which resonates with anecdotal use reported in this study.

By contrast, symptoms often cited elsewhere, including headache, nausea, stomach pain, and labour induction, did not emerge as significant predictors in this analysis. This contrasts with findings in Ethiopia, where Belayneh et al.

(2022) recorded high levels of herbal use for nausea and headache, in Saudi Arabia where Aljofan and Alkhamaiseh (2020) observed common use for labour facilitation, and in Tanzania where Mwakawanga et al. (2022) highlighted herbs as central for labour stimulation. Such differences suggest that cultural norms, symptom interpretation, and access to healthcare strongly influence herbal practices, and that motivations are not uniform across contexts. Importantly, positive beliefs proved stronger predictors than negative fears. The belief in protection from evil spirits ($B = 0.122$, $p = 0.037$), the prevention of heartburn ($B = 0.116$, $p = 0.028$), and the softening of the abdomen to ease fetal movement and prevent striae gravidarum ($B = 0.120$, $p = 0.036$) all significantly influenced herbal use. These findings resonate with Nik Yusof Fuad et al. (2020), who reported that women often rely on herbal remedies based on favourable outcomes observed in others, suggesting that lived experiences and spiritual assurances carry more weight than biomedical warnings. Conversely, concerns about stillbirth ($p = 0.915$), miscarriage ($p = 0.713$), or uterine rupture ($p = 0.963$) did not discourage use, reflecting what Silalahi et al. (2020) also observed that women often persist with herbs despite known risks, because perceived effectiveness and cultural acceptance remain dominant. The evidence indicates that maternal health behaviour is shaped less by awareness of risks and more by perceived benefits and cultural values.

Outcomes of the Use of Local Herbals in Maternity Care among Mothers in Nakaseke Town Council

The regression analysis in Table 11 shows that women's decisions to use herbal medicines in pregnancy are shaped more by perceived benefits than by awareness of risks. Three beliefs, namely protection from evil spirits ($B = 0.122$, $p = 0.037$), prevention of heartburn ($B = 0.116$, $p = 0.028$), and softening of the abdomen to ease fetal movement and reduce stretch marks ($B = 0.120$, $p = 0.036$), stood out as significant predictors. These reflect spiritual assurance, relief from discomfort, and concern for appearance, all of which hold strong meaning for expectant mothers. Similar findings were reported by Nabirye and Najjemba (2021), who highlighted the cultural importance of spiritual protection during pregnancy, while Tassew et al. (2024) observed that women frequently turn to herbal remedies as natural and safer alternatives to pharmaceuticals.

In contrast, adverse outcomes such as stillbirth ($B = -0.007$, $p = 0.915$), uterine rupture ($B = 0.003$, $p = 0.963$), and miscarriage ($B = 0.024$, $p = 0.713$) were not significant predictors of use. This indicates that warnings about risks have little effect since traditions, beliefs, and community influence outweigh fear of harm. Evidence from Solomon and Tesfaye (2022), and Babalola et al. (2021) confirms that women often continue to use herbs despite experiencing complications. Furthermore, Thipanyane et al. (2022) found that mothers persisted in using herbs for spiritual protection or labour relief

even after adverse outcomes, and Nik Yusof Fuad et al. (2020) similarly noted that cultural expectations and past benefits outweighed risk awareness. These findings confirm that cultural and experiential beliefs remain stronger motivators of maternal health behaviour than biomedical communication about risk.

Conclusion

The study confirmed that the use of herbal medicine in maternity care is highly prevalent among women in Nakaseke Town Council. A clear majority of mothers reported relying on herbs at some stage of pregnancy, labour, or the postpartum period, making traditional remedies a routine element of maternal care in the community. Despite improvements in access to biomedical facilities, women continued to depend on or complement them with local herbs, showing that traditional practice remains deeply embedded. Herbs were commonly employed for symptom relief, such as easing nausea, heartburn, and backache, as well as for labour induction and postpartum recovery. Strong cultural and spiritual motivations, including the belief in protection from harmful forces and the desire for smoother delivery, were also evident. Positive expectations consistently outweighed risk perceptions, as many mothers continued to use herbs even when complications were reported. The findings demonstrate that the use of herbs is not occasional but widespread, routine, and sustained by both cultural belief and perceived benefit. This underscores the importance of maternal health interventions that measure and address the persistence of these

practices, while promoting safer approaches through regulation, education, and collaboration between traditional and biomedical care providers.

Recommendations

Based on the findings, the following recommendations are proffered:

1. Health workers, especially midwives and nurses, should intensify antenatal and community education to address the widespread use of herbs. They should encourage mothers to combine safe cultural practices with biomedical care, reduce delays in reporting complications, and promote healthier maternal outcomes.

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2. Government and policymakers should strengthen policies guiding the role of traditional birth attendants. They should provide structured training, certification, and referral systems to prevent unsafe use of herbs in pregnancy or labour, while enhancing collaboration between TBAs and biomedical providers.

3. Public health authorities and maternal health educators should address the dominance of perceived benefits over risk awareness. They should design culturally sensitive messages that respect traditional beliefs yet clearly communicate risks, enabling women to make informed choices and avoid complications.

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